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ABSTRACT

In this study a regional simulation in Flanders, Belgium was performed with a Roth-C model to study the effect of reduced mineral fertilization on the soil organic carbon (SOC) stock. For this study, a model environment developed for a European scale simulation was used (Pape 2024) to determine the loss of SOC resulting from a reduced fertilization with a reduction of 20% N for seven crops (barley, grain maize, silage maize, potato, rapeseed, sugar beet and wheat). Data for the crop yield and area specific for Flanders were used to perform the simulation. The model environment uses yield reductions to simulate the impact on SOC of a reduction of 20% mineral N fertilization by simulating monocultures and using the share of agricultural area to find the resulting difference in SOC for each crop. The difference in C input is proportional to the yield reduction due to a reduction in fertilisation of -20% N, the yield and the crop's share of agricultural area. In the case study for Flanders a total of 0.84 Mg C/ha SOC loss over a period of 30 years was simulated. Most of this SOC loss was linked to cultivation of rapeseed and wheat, followed by grain and silage maize. In the simulation for Flanders higher SOC losses were found for the crops silage maize, grain maize, potatoes and sugar beet in comparison to the European scale simulation, while for the crops wheat, grain maize and barley a lower SOC loss was found. In Flanders maize is the most commonly grown crop, followed by cereals, potatoes and sugar beet. Due to a high share of area for these crops in Flanders high SOC losses were found, some higher than found in the European scale simulation. In the European scale and regional scale simulations, rapeseed has a high contribution to the simulated SOC losses, but this is rather linked to the high reduction in yield as a consequence of the reduction in mineral fertilization than due to the crop's share of total arable land. With the introduction of the regional specific data for yield and area, a more realistic simulation of the SOC losses were obtained due to the inclusion of detailed data on the crop's share of cultivated area. In Flanders, the agricultural area is very fragmented and scattered over all of Flanders. In European datasets this leads to very rough estimates of the amount of agricultural area which does not coincide with the reality. To further develop this scenario additional regional specific data such as climate, clay content and SOC content should be incorporated in the regional scale simulation.

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Introduction

A detailed case study on the effect of reduced mineral fertilization on the soil organic carbon stock (SOC) was performed in the region of Flanders, Belgium. In task 4.2, a European scale simulation was performed to determine the loss of SOC resulting from a reduced fertilization with a reduction of 20% N for seven crops (barley, grain maize, silage maize, potato, rapeseed, sugar beet and wheat). In this study, a regional simulation was performed with the model environment developed for the European scale simulation. Data for the crop yield and area specific for Flanders were used to perform the simulation.

Methodology

The model environment provided by task 4.2 was used to perform the detailed case study simulation (Pape 2024). This model environment uses the yield reductions from WP3 to simulate the impact on SOC of a reduction of 20% mineral N fertilization by simulating monocultures and using the share of agricultural area in a 10x10 km grid to find the resulting difference in SOC (Mg C/ha) for each crop. In the model environment the loss in SOC for barley, grain maize, potatoes, rapeseed, silage maize, sugar beet and wheat can be calculated. The model environment requires data on the climate (monthly temperature, monthly precipitation and monthly evapotranspiration), clay content, soil cover, crop yield and area. For the detailed case study, the data on the climate, clay content and soil cover from the European scale simulations were used (Pape 2024). Regional data for crop yield and area were used. The crop yield for barley, maize, silage maize, potato, rapeseed, sugar beet and wheat were obtained from STATBEL (STATBEL 2024) which contains statistics on the yield for the most common crops in Flanders. The yield data were converted to a raster layer in the correct unit (Mg/ha). The area data for each crop was obtained from the LPIS data for the year 2022 (Agentschap Landbouw en Zeevisserij 2024). The LPIS data contain the crops and cover crops cultivated on each agricultural parcel for each year. From this dataset the total area for barley, grain maize, silage maize, potato, rapeseed, sugar beet and wheat were extracted and converted to a raster layer. In the simulation the assumption was made that straw residues were not removed after harvest. The output of the model environment consists of a grid of 10x10 km with the SOC difference (Mg C/ha). The loss in SOC due to a reduction in fertilization is defined by the SOC difference (Mg C/ha). This difference is a function of the difference in C input coming from crops and local mineralisation conditions. The difference in C input is proportional to the yield reduction due to a reduction in fertilisation of -20% N, the yield and the crop's share of agricultural area. The SOC difference in a grid of 10x10 km was aggregated to the mean SOC difference for NUTS1 and NUTS2 levels.

Results and discussion

In Flanders a total loss of 0.84 Mg C/ha, due to the reduced mineral fertilisation of the 7 investigated crops, was found after a simulation of 30 years. The crops showing the highest SOC losses in Flanders are rapeseed followed by wheat (Figure 1 and Table 1).

Figure 1: SOC difference (Mg C/ha) at NUTS2 level for the crops barley, grain maize, potatoes, rapeseed, silage maize, sugar beet and wheat.

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In the European simulation an average SOC loss of 0.928 Mg C/ha was found after 30 years. The crops showing the highest SOC losses are wheat followed by rapeseed. The SOC loss for wheat is 0.17 Mg C/ha in Flanders, while in the European simulation the SOC loss is 0.353 Mg C/ha. The high SOC loss found for wheat is due to high wheat harvest residue and root biomass in comparison to the other simulated crops and the high share of total agricultural land (Pape 2024). The SOC loss found for rapeseed in Flanders was 0.26 Mg C/ha which is higher than the SOC loss of 0.220 Mg C/ha found for rapeseed in the European simulation. The high SOC loss found for rapeseed is linked to high yield reductions as was found in the European scale simulations (Pape 2024) but not due to a high share of area. In fact, rapeseed is the crop with the lowest share of area in the regional scale simulation (Table 1). In the regional case study a lower mean SOC difference was found for wheat, grain maize and barley in comparison to the European scale simulation. In the European scale simulations 0.183 Mg C/ha, 0.027 Mg C/ha and 0.04 Mg C/ha less SOC was lost after 30 years, respectively. However, potatoes, sugar beet, rapeseed and silage maize showed higher SOC losses in the regional scale simulation in Flanders. In the regional simulation, an additional SOC loss of 0.013 Mg C/ha, 0.016 Mg C/ha, 0.04 Mg C/ha and 0.010 Mg C/ha was found, respectively. Silage maize, potato and sugar beet are crops most commonly cultivated in Flanders (Table 1). As mentioned in the European scale simulation, the share of the crop in the total harvested area is an important driver for SOC loss. Since the regional scale simulation gave a higher share of these crops, higher SOC losses were found for crops in comparison to the European simulation. For the crop with the highest SOC loss (rapeseed) the highest range can be found between the minimum and maximum values found between the 10 x10 km grid. This indicates that the SOC losses for rapeseed are heterogeneously spatially distributed in Flanders. In Flanders rapeseed is not the most common crop grown in Flanders, however the SOC differences found at NUTS2 level (Table 1) indicate that regions with a larger share of area with rapeseed cultivated also have the highest SOC loss for this crop. In these regions the ranges between the minimum and maximum SOC differences found showed the most variation, indicating that in these regions the area with rapeseed cultivated is unequally distributed within these NUTS2 regions. The other crops simulated in the regional case study show a smaller variation between the minimum and maximum SOC differences found at regional and NUTS2 levels (Table 1). This indicates that in comparison to rapeseed the area on which these crops are cultivated is more equally distributed between the 10 x 10 km grids, which were aggregated to calculate the regional and NUTS2 level SOC difference. In the European simulation yield levels were the main driver for the SOC losses in Flanders since they are 45% above European average (Pape 2024). However, the regional case study indicates that a more detailed share of area can also have an impact on the SOC losses. In Flanders, the agricultural area is very fragmented and scattered. In European datasets this scattered fragmentation of agricultural area can lead to inaccurate estimates of the amount of agricultural area which does not coincide with the reality.

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Table 1: The mean soil organic carbon (SOC) difference (Mg C/ha), range of minimum and maximum SOC difference and area in Flanders and Flanders' NUTS2 regions found for barley, grain maize, potatoes, rapeseed, silage maize, sugarbeet and wheat.

crop	Mean SOC difference (Mg C/ha)	Range SOC difference (Mg C/ha)	Area (ha)	NUTS2 code	NUTS2 name	Mean SOC difference (Mg C/ha)	Range SOC difference (Mg C/ha)	Area (ha)
Barley	0.07	0.02-0.19	16228	BE21	Antwerpen	0.06	0.03 – 0.12	649
				BE22	Limburg	0.06	0.02 – 0.19	3368
				BE23	Oost-Vlaanderen	0.08	0.02 – 0.17	3437
				BE24	Vlaams-Brabant	0.06	0.03 – 0.12	4996
				BE25	West-Vlaanderen	0.07	0.02 – 0.14	3778
Grain maize	0.15	0.03 - 0.46	52361	BE21	Antwerpen	0.17	0.05 – 0.46	5780
				BE22	Limburg	0.16	0.06 – 0.38	6589
				BE23	Oost-Vlaanderen	0.16	0.06 – 0.35	14803
				BE24	Vlaams-Brabant	0.11	0.03 – 0.23	11253
				BE25	West-Vlaanderen	0.14	0.07 – 0.30	13936
Potatoes	0.02	0.01 - 0.04	53168	BE21	Antwerpen	0.02	0.01 – 0.04	4947
				BE22	Limburg	0.02	0.01 – 0.04	3794
				BE23	Oost-Vlaanderen	0.02	0.01 – 0.04	12750
				BE24	Vlaams-Brabant	0.01	0.01 – 0.02	6088
				BE25	West-Vlaanderen	0.02	0.01 – 0.03	25588
Rapeseed	0.26	0.00 - 1.32	706	BE21	Antwerpen	0.11	0.00 – 0.48	22
				BE22	Limburg	0.34	0.00 – 1.32	53
				BE23	Oost-Vlaanderen	0.13	0.01 – 0.49	31
				BE24	Vlaams-Brabant	0.47	0.09 – 1.06	483
				BE25	West-Vlaanderen	0.24	0.00 – 0.81	117

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Silage maize	0.13	0.05 – 0.41	127377	BE21	Antwerpen	0.16	0.06 – 0.31	29128
				BE22	Limburg	0.13	0.06 – 0.21	16504
				BE23	Oost-Vlaanderen	0.13	0.06 – 0.41	35813
				BE24	Vlaams-Brabant	0.12	0.05 – 0.22	9569
				BE25	West-Vlaanderen	0.13	0.06 – 0.21	36363
Sugarbeet	0.04	0.00 – 0.08	18316	BE21	Antwerpen	0.03	0.00 – 0.06	674
				BE22	Limburg	0.03	0.00 – 0.07	4053
				BE23	Oost-Vlaanderen	0.03	0.01 – 0.07	2906
				BE24	Vlaams-Brabant	0.04	0.01 – 0.07	4329
				BE25	West-Vlaanderen	0.04	0.01 – 0.08	6354
Wheat	0.17	0.00 – 0.61	62820	BE21	Antwerpen	0.13	0.00 – 0.28	1397
				BE22	Provincie Limburg	0.16	0.03 – 0.61	9110
				BE23	Oost-Vlaanderen	0.16	0.08 – 0.34	12152
				BE24	Vlaams-Brabant	0.19	0.09 – 0.43	16779
				BE25	West-Vlaanderen	0.18	0.11 – 0.41	23236

Conclusion

In the case study for Flanders a total of 0.84 Mg C/ha SOC loss over a period of 30 years was simulated with a reduction of -20% N in mineral fertilization. Most of this SOC loss was linked to cultivation of rapeseed and wheat, followed by grain and silage maize. The most important driver for SOC loss is the crop's share of total arable land. In the simulation for Flanders this leads to higher SOC losses found for the crops silage maize, grain maize, potatoes and sugar beet in comparison to the European scale simulation, while for the crops wheat, grain maize and barley a lower SOC loss was found. In Flanders maize is the most commonly grown crop, followed by cereals, potatoes and sugar beet. Due to the high share of agricultural area for these crops, high SOC losses were found with some higher than found in the European scale simulation. In the European scale and regional scale simulations, rapeseed has a high contribution to the simulated SOC losses, but this is rather linked to the high reduction in yield as a consequence of the reduction in mineral fertilization than due to the crop's share of total arable land.

With the introduction of the regional specific data for yield and area, a more realistic simulation of the SOC losses were obtained due to the inclusion of detailed data on the crop's share of cultivated area. In Flanders, the agricultural area is very fragmented and scattered. In European datasets this fragmentation can lead to inaccurate estimates of the amount of agricultural area which does not coincide with the reality. To further develop this scenario additional regional specific data such as regional yield data, climate, clay and SOC content should be incorporated in the regional scale simulation.

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